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Asynchronous Technology Utilized By Biology Teachers In Public Secondary Schools In Awka South Local Government Area Of Anambra State, Nigeria

Dr. Ezeobi Gloria Ogechukwu

**Department of Science Education,
Faculty of Education,**

Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.

Email: go.ezeobi@unzik.edu.ng, Phone Number: 08037640850

ABSTRACT

The study investigated asynchronous technology utilized by biology teachers in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 58 biology teachers in public secondary schools in Awka South LGA in Anambra State, Nigeria. The instruments for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher which was validated by three experts. The instrument yielded reliability coefficient values of 0.87, 0.88 and 0.84 for clusters 1, 2 and 3 respectively with an overall coefficient value of 0.86. Mean was used to answer the research questions. Findings of the study revealed that biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms, blogs and e-mail in public secondary schools to a low extent in Anambra State of Nigeria. Based on these findings, the researcher recommended among others that administrators of secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria, should organize regular digital literacy workshops and training for biology teachers to improve their skills in using online discussion platforms. It was further recommended that heads of biology units in secondary schools should encourage the integration of blogging into the curriculum by providing biology teachers with the necessary tools and training on how to use blogs as an educational tool.

Keywords: Asynchronous technology, utilization, schools, biology teachers.

INTRODUCTION

Education has been the pillar of development in the universe, the light of civilization in the world, the fuel of harmonization, across continents, the booster of economy of nations, the principal development and growth of all countries. The education system has been affected by several challenges, the deadliest was the closing down of the educational sector due to widespread pandemic diseases. The World Health Organization (W.H.O) in 2020 declared Covid-19 in March 2020 as a global pandemic, in other to minimizing the spread of the virus, various governments established, curfew and lockdown, in workplace, suspension of transport facilities and so on. Dan-Nwafor, Ochu, Elimian, Oladejo, Ilori, Umeokonkwo and Ihekweazu (2020) stated that educational institutions was temporarily closed down by most countries around the world Nigeria inclusive. This made over 90 percent of students population of the world affected by the structure of teaching, learning and assessment nationwide.

Biology is a popular science subject taught at the senior secondary school level. One primary function of biology teaching is to help the students understand biology concept, principles, theories and laws. According to Gbamanja (2022) biology teaching involves exposing the students to several opportunities

to understand different types of concepts and principles. This also expose the students to direct physical materials that will make some meaning to the cognitive framework. The implication is that biology teaching must be effective and meaningful to achieve its goals. Matazu (2022) stressed that biology education expose learners to processes and attitudes as well as equips them with professional skills of a biology teacher. Biology teachers have therefore both biological knowledge as well as skills for impartation of such knowledge to the students. This makes them the implementers of the curriculum, a role that places the teachers at very strategic positions in the entire educational and societal development programmes. The teaching of biology according to Oyovwi (2022) should help the student comprehend the world around him and also better prepare him to improve on it.

Oyovwi further stated that biology teaching enables the child among others to acquire basic scientific knowledge and also help him to discover the order and complex of the universe. Based on this, they further believed that the child should be given first hand familiarity with the variety of biological, physical and man-made phenomena in the world around him.

Asynchronous Technology: Asynchronous leaning can be defined as learning in which interaction between instructors and students occurs intermittently with a time delay (Van der Keylen, Lipert, Kunishc, Kuhlem and Roo, 2020). Asynchronous setting are classified as more individually based and self-placed, as well as less instructor-dependent and are temporally and geographically independent. They do, however, provide obstacles as the media richness and media naturalness approaches imply. The media richness approach describes a medium as “ability to provide immediate feedback, transmit verbal and non-verbal communication cues; provide a sense of personalization and simulate a natural language, whereas face-to-face communication is considered to be the most natural form of communication. As a result, synchronous leaning settings are less natural and “rich” than face-to-face learning environment (Ogbonna, Ibezim and Obi, 2019).

Asynchronous e-learning is a type of e-learning that makes learning available as soon as or whenever it is required, giving learners great flexibility in terms of time, process and content. Many of the existing e-learning systems offer asynchronous learning environments because they are easy to set up and cheaper than synchronous e-learning methods. Ogbonna, et. al (2019) stated that asynchronous allows users to use applications such as email, blogs, wikis, discussion boards, we-supported textbooks, hypertext documents, audio or video courses and social networking using web 2.0, learners complete course work, discussions, questions et cetera in their own time. Ogbonna et al noted that asynchronous technology is mainly self-induced and occurs at the leisure time of the learner and their preferred venue. It is a form of learning that occurs independently through e-books or CD-ROM guides, or through others, e-mail, online newsletter boards and discussion platforms.

Online Discussion Platforms: An online discussion platforms (ODPF) is a web-based tool that connects people that have similar interests and perspectives. Online discussion platforms have become a popular tool and successful method for involving students outside of the classroom (Alabo and Emmah, 2014) ODPF are text-based asynchronous discussion used in online learning. Several educational best practices for students and instructors are integrated into online discussion platforms. ODPF is an online learning platform that gives students the ability to add messages to discussion threads, engage with other students and instructors and receive feedback (Lowenthal, Borup, West and Archambault, 2020). This allows students to gain a deeper grasp of the topics being discussed. They have been used in education to supplement conventional teaching methods like lectures and tutorials (Ferlazzo, 2020).

Alabo and Emmah (2014) were of the opinion that all students must respond to prompts and interact with their peers. This will enable students to have more time to establish thoughts and respond carefully to others. The students will also spend more time constructing grammatically accurate solutions, which will help them write better. Online discussion boards give students a place to study, debate and reinforce the topics covered in class according to Alabo and Emmah (2014).

Several studies have found that online discussion platforms are beneficial in developing communication skills. The Computer Mediated Communication (CMC) has a positive potential to increase interaction

among students. Online platforms are a good way of communicating especially when the teacher or lecturer is unavailable. It is also a good way to communicate with everyone as it creates good communication between students and school. Students are more comfortable and less aggressive when participating in online platforms. Online platforms also offered more equal opportunities for group members to voice their opinions. They demonstrate very high levels of interaction among group members. Online platforms are regarded as a social interaction that reduces student's reliance on face-to-face discussions.

Lowenthal, et. al (2020) stated that online discussion platforms enables the students to collaborate on projects in small groups, participate in ongoing discussions about course content and present group project products to the rest of the class. All of this is done regardless of the student's location or time of participation in the discussion platforms. This is coordinated with a separate website for an online course's readings and assignments. Making weekly participation in the discussion a requirement "institutionalizes" the discussion platforms within the course. There is evidence that messages written by students in online platforms include longer problem-solving solutions and deeper reflections than face-to-face discussions (Lowenthal, et. al, 2020).

Blogs: Blogs can be used in teaching for writing reflections on lectures and presentations made in class, as a continuation of classroom discussion, for case study discussion, for raising questions and getting answers about practices, procedures, assignments, activities and topics not covered during class sessions, and, as a resource hub for exchanging teaching and learning aid (Elega and Ozad, 2017). A blog is a website that features the experiences, observations and opinions of one or more writers. It also frequently includes images and links to other websites. These two technologies have the potential to lower classroom barriers and boost students' intrinsic motivation to learn science. Elega and Ozad (2017) stated that due to students' interest in using these technologies, blogs could help students learn things outside of the classroom. It is essential to establish a setting that supports the collaborative and individualized learning of writing skills before providing learners with writing tools. Through blogging, students can not only enhance their writing abilities but also develop their writing confidence and reach a larger audience. In time, students with varied interests can become famous bloggers with large audiences and can take ownership of their blogging-based writing. Additionally, blogging techniques actively encourage students to try new things, take calculated risks and develop their awareness of writing for both private and public audiences. Through blogging, students can write freely and when read or published, can draw on a variety of ideas from one another. Kim in Kilic and Godkas (2014) stated the weblogs and blogs, respectively, are online journals where authors post a series of chronological, editable entries or posts on a topic that is usually of personal interest to the author and is frequently expressed in a highly subjective voice. Readers are encouraged to leave comments on these online journals. Blog may contain text, attachments to files, link to web pages, video, audio and multimedia content.

Blogs can help differentiate instruction, boost student motivation, test students' critical thinking skills, expand the boundaries of the classroom and capitalize on student's interest in technology. Students gain writing and communication skills through the use of blogs and they also get a chance to think about issues from the real world.

Kim in Kulie and Godkas (2014) were of the view that students gain writing and communication skills through the use of blogs and they also get a chance to think about issues from the real world. The silent student or a student who is uncomfortable speaking in front of the class, can be given a voice through blogs. For these students, the blog can provide a safe place where their voices can be heard in a less stressful setting. Blogs have the potential to reach a wider audience because they are public. In essence, blogs can be used in a learning environment for collaborative knowledge construction through inquiry-based interaction.

Kim in Kulie and Godkas (2014) asserts that integrating web 2.0 tools into instruction was a stimulating and innovative experience for both teachers and students. As a result of the material's relevance, freshness and practicality, their students were interested in it.

Blogs can be used very simply to create e-portfolio (electronic portfolio and digital portfolio). Even though the potential of blog use in increasing student interactivity and collaboration has been explored by many educators, research conducted on the effectiveness of blog use in the educational context is still quite limited and considered as a contradictory research area. In other words, some research results show that blogs are an effective tool for enhancing students' online engagement in online activity.

E-mail: The e-mail is an acronym for electronic mail. E-mail is a widely used internet application that enables individuals or groups of individuals to quickly exchange messages, even if they are separated by long distances.

Epignosis (2014) stated that electronic mail (e-mail) is a computer-based program that allows users to exchange messages. Electronic mail, often known as e-mail, is a way of sending digital communications from one author to one or more receivers. E-mail or electronic mail is the delivery of communications (as basic and straight forward as letter writing) over electronic networks such as the internet. Epignosis stated that people may exchange e-mail messages relatively faster to a global e-mail network. The e-mail is the electronic version of a letter but with time and flexibility advantages. That a letter can take anywhere from one day to a couple of weeks to arrive, an e-mail is virtually immediately set to the intended recipient's mailbox, generally in the multiple-second to sub-minute range. Modern e-mail is sent and received through the internet or other computer networks. Electronic mail is a type of text communication that can include files, photos or other attachments that is transmitted across a network to a specific individual or group of individuals. A letter delivered through the internet to a receiver is known as electronic mail.

According to Epignosis (2014) some electronic mail systems are limited to a single computer or network, whilst others include gateways to other computer systems, allowing users to send electronic communications anywhere in the globe because it is quick, flexible and dependable. Epignosis also stated that sent messages are stored in electronic mail boxes until they are retrieved by the receiver. To see if you have any mail, you may need to check your electronic mailbox on a regular basis (just like you would for the postal mailbox), but many systems will notify you when mail is received. After viewing the message, it may be saved as a text file, printed on paper, forwarded to other users or deleted.

Adeoye and Adanikin (2020) detailed the advantages and marvels of utilizing email, which included the following:

1. **Convenience:** If a desktop computer, laptop or mobile phone is nearby, users may compose electronic messages wherever they are, save them for later use and send them at any time without worrying about envelopes, stamps or tariffs.
2. **Speed:** E-mails often reach within seconds or minutes anywhere in the globe, which can only be claimed for a small percentage of letters received through postal mail.
3. **Attachments:** Electronic messaging programmes enable you to effortlessly attach any file on your computer to an email message regardless of its kind or most cases, size. It is just as simple to send a long master's thesis over the world as it is to email or a spread sheet.
4. **Accessibility:** Electronic communication can be easily kept in the email application. Good systems make it simple to organize, archive and search emails, ensuring that any information included in an email is always available.
5. **Cost:** With the exception of the charge paid for internet connection, sending and receiving emails is normally free. Gmail.com, yahoo.com, outlook.com, mail.com, vandex mail, hush mail, zoho mail and more popular email servers (Adeoye and Adanikin, 2020).

Purpose of the Study

The study determined the extent of asynchronous technology utilized by biology teachers in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.

Specifically, it determined;

1. The extent to which biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.

2. The extent to which biology teachers utilize blogs in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.
3. The extent to which biology teachers utilize e-mail in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent do biology teachers utilize blogs in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria?
3. To what extent do biology teachers utilize e-mail in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria?

RESEARCH METHODS

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. A descriptive survey is a method of obtaining information from various groups or person mainly through groups or persons mainly through questionnaire or personal interviews in order to provide a relative complete understanding of what is happening at a given period and time (Nworgu, 2015). This design is considered appropriate for the study because the researcher used questionnaire to determine the extent asynchronous technology is used by biology teachers in teaching biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 58 biology teachers from the 18 public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. The sample of the study comprised 58 biology teachers from the 18 public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria. The researcher sampled the entire population of the study because it was manageable.

The researcher developed questionnaires titled “Asynchronous Technology Utilized by Teachers for Teaching Biology in Public Secondary Schools” (ATUTTBPSS). The questionnaire has two parts: namely A and B. Part A contains information on the background information of the respondents covering gender while part B is divided into three clusters; cluster B1 contains 6 items on the extent teachers used online discussion platforms in teaching biology, cluster B2 contains 5 items on the extent biology teachers use blogs in teaching biology and cluster B3 contains 6 items on the extent biology teachers use e-mail in teaching biology. In all, part B contains 17 item statements. The instrument is structured on a four point rating scale on Very High Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE) – 3 points, Low Extent (LE) – 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) – 1 point.

Validation of the Instrument: To ascertain the validity of the instrument for the study, the research questions, purpose of the study and the 18 items questionnaire were given to three experts in the Department of Science Education and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation Unit of Educational Foundations Department, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State of Nigeria. These experts were requested to validate the instrument relative to the appropriateness and coverage of the items, wordings and item construct as well as clarity of the instructions.

Reliability of the Instrument: To establish the instrument’s reliability, it was administered on a sample of 20 biology teachers in public secondary schools in Onitsha South Local Government Area of Anambra State who are not included in the population of the study area. The application of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 using Cronbach Alpha reliability method on the obtained data yielded at score of 0.86 for internal consistency which was deemed reliable for the study. As a result of the fact that the instrument is in three clusters, the researcher had to ascertain the reliability of each cluster using Cronbach Alpha reliability method which yielded coefficient values of 0.87, 0.88 and 0.84 for clusters B1, B2 and B3 respectively. These coefficient values indicate that the instrument is highly reliable. This was based on Nworgu (2015) who stated that coefficient value of 0.70 and above is reliable.

Method of Data Collection: Data was collected by the researcher with the help of three research assistants who are biology teachers in secondary schools and each was assigned to schools. The research assistants were briefed by the researcher on the content and mode of the instruments administration. The questionnaire was administered by the research assistants on the spot to the biology teachers in their offices.

Method of Data Analysis: The data collected for the study was analyzed using mean. The mean value was used to answer the research questions. Decision on the research questions was based on the item and cluster mean score in relation to the cut off mean score of 2.50. Thus, an item or cluster with mean score of 2.50 or higher is high extent, while, any item or cluster below 2.50 is low extent.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent do biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Teachers response on the extent biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N	\bar{X}	DECISION
1.	I use discussion platforms like YouTube to engage students in activities related to topics in biology	58	1.06	Low Extent
2.	I create discussion topics in reedit where students can express their views on topics in biology.	58	1.32	Low Extent
3.	I encourage peer-to-peer learning by assigning group discussions to students in online discussion forums like now comment.	58	1.33	Low Extent
4.	I refer students to online discussion forums like biology forums to get more clarity on concepts in biology.	58	1.42	Low Extent
5.	I create interactive quizzes related to biology topics to assess students understanding in biology labs online forum.	58	1.28	Low Extent
6.	I share videos on YouTubes on topics in Biology to aid students understanding of difficult concepts.	58	1.54	Low Extent
GRAND MEAN			1.32	Low Extent

Data in Table 1 reveal that the respondents rated items, 1-6 on the extent biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria with mean ratings ranging between 1.06 and 1.54 to a low extent. The grand mean of 1.32 indicate that biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State to a low extent.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do biology teachers utilize blogs in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Teachers response on the extent Biology teachers utilize blogs in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N	\bar{X}	DECISION
7.	I use blogs to post class schedules	58	1.75	Low Extent
8.	I post subject materials to students in blogs	58	1.43	Low Extent
9.	I use blogs as platforms for group projects where students can collectively write about a specific topic in biology	58	1.20	Low Extent
10.	I use blog to discuss recent discoveries in biology	58	1.11	Low Extent
11.	I post articles related to biology topics for students to explore	58	1.50	Low Extent
GRAND MEAN			1.39	Low Extent

Data in Table 2 reveals that respondents opinion on items 7 – 11 on the extent biology teachers utilize blogs in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria with mean ratings ranging between 1.11 and 1.75 to a low extent. The grand mean of 1.39 indicates that biology teachers utilize blogs in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State to a low extent.

Research Question 3: *To what extent do biology teachers utilize e-mail in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Teachers response on the extent biology teachers utilize e-mails in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N	\bar{X}	DECISION
12.	I use the e-mail to send out assessment reports to the head of Department in Biology.	58	1.33	Low Extent
13.	I use the e-mail to get feedback from biology stents at any time.	58	1.47	Low Extent
14.	I send reminders about upcoming quizzes to students through e-mail.	58	1.21	Low Extent
15.	I send notifications about upcoming laboratory sessions to students through e-mail.	58	1.09	Low Extent
16.	I use the e-mail to facilitate my professional development by subscribing to biology related newsletters.	58	1.12	Low Extent
17.	I use the e-mail to invite professionals in the field of biology to update students on the current trends in biology.	58	1.23	Low Extent
GRAND MEAN			1.24	Low Extent

Data in Table 3 reveals that respondents opinion on items 12 – 17 on the extent Biology teachers utilize e-mail in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria with mean ratings ranging between 1.09 and 1.47 to a low extent. The grand mean of 1.24 indicate that biology teachers utilize e-mail in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria to a low extent.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria to a low extent. This is because some biology teachers may lack sufficient access to reliable internet, computers or other necessary devices, making it difficult for them to engage in online discussion platforms effectively. Accordingly, some biology teachers may not have received adequate training on how to use online platforms for educational purposes, leading to reluctance or difficulty in incorporating these tools into their teaching practices. This is in line with Mabalane (2021) who reported that teachers lacked the necessary ICT skills needed for online instructional delivery.

Further findings indicated that biology teachers utilize blogs in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria to a low extent. This may have resulted because some biology teachers may not have received adequate training in using blogs as an educational tool, leading to a lack of confidence in creating and managing blog content effectively. This is in agreement with Isiyaka (2021) who reported that teachers were aware of blogs though they still had insufficient information of its use in learning.

Mabalane (2021) also noted that blogs were not effectively utilized by teachers. Isiyaku (2021) opined that privacy issues, solitary led insufficient information still limited the adoption of blogs in learning in Nigeria.

Further, result showed that biology teachers utilize e-mail in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria to a low extent. This is because biology teachers might see the use of email as more suited for administrative purposes rather than as a tool for teaching or engaging with students in the learning environment. This finding is in disagreement with Aladi, Samuel and Ibrahim (2023) who reported that the use of asynchronous technologies like e-mails is effective for teaching. Enweta (2016) stated that the application of asynchronous technology like e-mail will help to promote effective feedback between students and teachers.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was concluded that biology teachers utilize asynchronous technology in the teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria to a low extent. The biology teachers utilize online discussion platforms, blogs and e-mail in teaching biology in public secondary schools in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria to a low extent. It is therefore imperative that measures are put in place to improve the integration of asynchronous technology by biology teachers in teaching of biology in public secondary schools in Anambra State of Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Administrators of secondary schools should organize regular digital literacy workshops and training for biology teachers to improve their skills in using online discussion platforms. Along the line, secondary school administrators should invest in reliable internet infrastructure to facilitate teachers' and students' access to these platforms, thereby, promoting collaborative learning and fostering greater interaction outside of classroom hours.
2. The heads of biology units in secondary schools should encourage the integration of blogging into the curriculum by providing biology teachers with the necessary tools and training on how to use blogs as an educational tool. The biology teachers should be shown the benefits of blogs for reflective learning and given support to create subject specific blogs where students can discuss topics, share ideas, and receive feedback on their understanding of biology concepts.

3. The administrators of secondary schools should enhance communication between teachers and students, schools should promote the use of e-mail as an essential tool for educational correspondence. This can be achieved by setting clear guideline on e-mail usage for both biology teachers and biology students. This will ensure that it is effectively used for sharing resources, assignments and clarifying questions outside the classroom.

Nonetheless, biology teachers should be encouraged to check and respond to e-mails regularly to maintain efficient communication.

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